

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: APOLLO****FIRST NAME: AFRICA SENDAHANGARWA****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 11%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 11

List your 5-7 critical concepts with the page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Essay Writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 6-12)
2. American vs. British English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 24-32)
3. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 33-39)
4. Chicago Manual of Style (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 43-56)
5. How to write a response paper (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024)

INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING AT EUCLID UNIVERSITY

1) INTRODUCTION

After enrolling in the Doctorate (Ph.D.) in Diplomacy and International Affairs at EUCLID University, the initial course is ACA-401D International Academic Writing (Doctorate). This is a course that initiates a student into the program. My experience with it is that it removes the excitement from the student of enrolling into a doctorate program and instead brings more confusion and doubt if one will be able to make it through the program. This confusion is mostly combined with the fact that the program is distance learning and the interaction between the student and the instructor is virtual; thus, it is initially difficult to seek and get academic support as a new student.

However, as the student makes it through the initiation documents where instructions for accessing the course content are delivered, the confusion slowly clears even though the tension may increase. The platforms are the Course Management System (CMS) and the Learning Management System (LMS). The student is guided to log in on both platforms to access his/her course content and follow up on his/her performance, assignments, and other academic requirements by the instructor or the university.

The module has one video titled Basic ACA-401 Tutorial with narration about using styles in Word as required by the university standards. In the video, the narrator (Laurent Cleenewerck) opens a response paper template in Word and advises students to personalize the template and save it from being reused in all response papers. The video demonstrates how to edit the template from the header to how the document is expected to be formatted and the size of the response paper. It also advises the student to show the instructor that he/she has interacted with the study content. The visitor also advises the student to choose and indicate the language that he/she will be using, which should be either English United States or English United Kingdom. He demonstrates how to set up the proofing language for the document. He states, “It is not only the spelling of some words that are going to be affected but also where you are going to put a full stop or period when you use quotation marks.” He mentions that “the rule is very simple; in UK English, the full stop is always placed after the quotation marks while in US English, the period is always placed before the last quotation marks.”

The preliminary information on the LMS for this module instructs the student to download the assigned study material from the school’s *Egnyte* cloud-based file repository. The module continues by informing the student that one or more *Vimeo* password-protected videos may be provided as mandatory or supplemental course material. The notes continue by informing the student that the video should be interacted with in the response paper and referenced using the Turabian in-text style if the video is mandatory. The study material provided to download and study is titled ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack (Period 1). This course pack is a 72-page document with eight chapters (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 4–5). However, in this response paper, my discussion will concentrate on the following: essay writing, American vs. British English, plagiarism, style guide, and the Chicago Manual of Style. I will also write on how to write a response paper as guided by Prof. Cleenewerck and Dr. Gulma (2024, 2-11).

2) ESSAY WRITING

This is the first chapter of ACA-401/ACA-401D, as mentioned in the introduction above. It discusses a general overview of the basics of essay writing, steps for writing a good essay, and some rules of thumb for writing a paper. The chapter describes academic essay or scholarly writing as nonfictional writing produced as part of academic work. It gives examples of such writings as research findings and empirical fieldwork, which may or may not be published in journals, books, newspapers or periodicals, conference papers, technical reports, and students’ presentations.

The chapter denotes that all academic papers are based on evidence to communicate ideas that seek to provide answers to prove or disprove hypotheses. It indicates that most academic writings reference and cite other works, use stable rhetorical moves to define the paper’s scope and the relevance of that research and provide new contributions to the topic (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7).

a) Starting the essay

There are basic steps to be considered to write an academic essay. The chapter highlights the following three as required before starting the essay: early start-up, defining the question and analyzing the task, and drafting an initial plan.

In this section, Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma advise that it is always better to start as early as possible because one of the key things required for writing is to have enough time to read and do your research about the topic you want to write about. The source indicates that, while defining and writing everything one knows about the topic is important, presenting the answers to the research question after analyzing it is key. Drafting a plan for writing the essay is very important. The plan should include initial thoughts about the topic. The source indicates that if an essay plan is well written, it will assist the writer how in answering the question and guide him/her on which information to use.

b) Researching the topic

The next important thing is to read and understand what you have to write. Reading and researching will provide factual information to develop an academic discussion while providing answer(s) to the question(s). While researching on the topic, the following questions must be answered: what the researcher already knows about the topic, what he/she does not know and thus needs to research to write the paper, if the material being gathered is helpful to the topic/discussion, and if the material can be used to support the answer(s) being provided by the paper.

The lecturers advise the student researcher to make notes while researching the topic since those notes taken will be the basis for developing academic writing. The student researcher is also advised to highlight or underline relevant information that he will return to when re-reading the text and taking more notes. Notes should come from any information source, including bibliographic details like the author's name, date, title, publisher, place of publication, and any other relevant details.

c) Organizing your ideas in a plan

After reading and researching the topic, your ideas become more developed; it is time to write an essay plan to help answer the research question and structure your writing. The plan should be drawn factoring in the following: a possible answer to the research question, selected information to be used in answering the research question, examples to provide evidence to support your answer, and points and the order in which you will discuss them.

d) Producing a draft

The essay mentioned above will give you a basis for developing your draft writing. The draft is more of something to refine by editing and redrafting. Adding details gives you what to work with to produce a refined paper.

The structure of the paper should be in the format of an Introduction, Body, and Conclusion. The introduction starts with a broad opening of topic areas, answering the research question with a thesis statement and providing a summary of your paper, from general to specific. The body of the paper consists of paragraphs that create a logical progression in discussion. This part of the paper also brings out the evidence to develop the argument by using examples and authoritative quotations. The conclusion re-summarizes the main points of the discussion and includes a final broad statement with possible implications and possible directions for future research. It is prohibited to introduce any new information in the conclusion.

3) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

According to Cleenewerck and Gulma (2024, 25), American and British are both variants of world English and are more similar than different. It is indicated that most divergence can be ascribed to different national histories and cultural development. There are general categories of difference between standard American English and standard British English, basically in pronunciation with the exact spelling and some with different spelling with the same pronunciation.

There is a notable difference in the usage of collective nouns like ‘has’ for the US vs ‘have’ by the British. Usage of ‘it’ by the US vs ‘they’ by the British while refereeing to a team. Some other differences can be noted in the usage of pluralized adjectives by the British, while in American English, they are not. An example is “drugs test” in British English while it is “drug test” in American English, or “careers guidance” in British English while it is just “career guidance” in American English.

There are also notable differences in current events and events, euphemistic references, and writing of dates, among others.

4) PLAGIARISM

ACA-401/ACA-401D defined plagiarism as when the writer uses sources of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 34). Plagiarism can be intentional or unintentional, and writers must acknowledge the sources of information from which they get information. Failure to acknowledge other writers’ work or sources of information depicts the writer as disrespectful to other writers and thus should be deemed incompetent and should not be accorded recognition as a writer.

It is good that this program at EUCLID University starts with a course on International Academic Writing, which addresses plagiarism. This prepares students like myself to start their academic journey with this in mind and raise their writing standards free of this serious academic offense. Students are guided to give credit to the source of their information by using a quote, paraphrasing, statistical data, or visuals.

Writers need to consider that there are two things they need to be aware of when citing works used. Those things are in-text citations and a list of works cited. In-text citation refers to citing pieces of work used within the actual text itself. In this case, the writer is advised to use the content in his/her paper and then put the author's name in parentheses with a page number where the information was cited. This type of citation can be used as quotations or paraphrasing. Quotations are the exact words of the author, while paraphrasing is using your own words to write an idea or information that another author has produced on the topic. In both cases, you must indicate the source of such information because not doing so amounts to plagiarism.

Everything written cannot be cited. Therefore, it is essential to address the issue of when not to cite, which does not amount to plagiarism. The general rule is that if the information being used is common knowledge and can be found in various public places, there is no need to cite the source. If the information has been repeated in many different writings widely distributed for an extended period, then it can be considered common knowledge.

5) **CHICAGO MANUAL OF STYLE**

The Chicago style is the style of formatting books and research papers documented in the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) and Kate Turabian's Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations. Both manuals were published by the University of Chicago Press in 2003 and 1996. The latter was revised in 2006. The style provides standards for the usage of abbreviations and acronyms, capitalization of words, usage of compound words, format for writing numbers and dates, and usage of quotations. It also describes formatting pages, including titles and headings, lists and tables, footnotes, and a bibliography (Cleenewerck and Gulma, 2024, 44).

Chicago style usage recommends "using *Webster's Third New International Dictionary* and its chief abridgment, Merriam-Webster's Collegiate Dictionary, for general spelling. If the Collegiate disagrees with the *Third International*, the *Collegiate* should be followed since it represents the latest lexical research."

The Chicago style indicates that abbreviations should be used only in contexts where they are straightforward to readers. It is recommended that when first used in the text, acronyms should be introduced by placing the acronym or its source phrase in parentheses and, after that, using just the acronym.

The style provides more detailed standards on writing, including rules on capitalization, internet terminologies, compound words, italics and quotation marks,

numbers and date formats, quotations, page formats, footnotes, headings and lists, tables, endnotes and footnotes, and bibliographies.

6) HOW TO WRITE A RESPONSE PAPER

According to Cleenewerck and Gulma (2024, 2), a response paper has four parts: a summary of the material studied, the student's reaction to the study material, the conclusion, and the references. The authors indicate that the first part is just like the abstract of a technical report, and the following should be captured in this part. Title of the work and its authors, including the publisher's name and year of publication in parenthesis, contents of the material showcased by the main ideas, and informative supporting points that give the reader a general sense of the main ideas of the original work. This part should also use direct quotations from the work to illustrate the main ideas. In this part, the writer is advised not to go into detail about any idea. The summary should remain objective and factual as the writer should not give his/her personal reaction in this part since the subjective impression of the author will form the second part of the paper.

The second part of the paper is the subjective impression of the study material. Students are advised to include the following points when writing this part. The student is advised to pick at least five concepts among the many discussed in the material. The student is also reminded to avoid plagiarism, which could be caused by copying and pasting study material into the response paper. Personal pronouns in this part are highly recommended to provide a personal reaction to the study material. Description of how the study material relates to students' personal experiences, feelings, and life in general (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 3).

The response paper's conclusion should summarize what was learned and how the study material was perceived, and an objective evaluation is expected to be made. The student is encouraged to critique the study material by indicating whether they agree with certain points or not and providing supporting reasons for their position.

The last part of the response paper is the list of references. The references are based on the rule of style chosen by the student. It is essential to consider some points while writing the paper at Euclid University. It is important to be clear about the type of English, whether it is US or UK, the rule of style, and whether Zotero software was used. It is also a requirement that the student use the provided template while writing a coherent, clear, and error-free sentence using Grammarly software as guided and provided by the university. The student should organize the paper in the summary of ideas, their reaction to ideas, and the conclusion by using transition words and phrases for a smooth flow of ideas from one part to another.

7) CONCLUSION

This being my initial interaction with the PhD program and my initial response paper, I am between excitement and confusion. The style and intensity of writing papers at

Euclid University are new to me. The usage of the Chicago Manual of Style is new and exciting. I have never used Grammarly before to check my grammar while writing, and I must confess that I am excited to see and correct my grammar mistakes as I write.

Reading and internalizing the content from the study material provided was very enriching and eye-opening, as was what is awaiting me in this program. The course pack, orientation documents, and videos all provide a sense of how the program will be covered and what I am expected of. I look forward to seeing how I do with this first response paper so that I can build on it to move forward till the end of the program and get my doctorate degree.

REFERENCES

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